

Reflections on professional growth within the field of mathematics education

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Being involved in a teaching development project as university teachers and researchers of mathematics education, we started to critically reflect on professional growth within our specific situation. We developed our own understanding of professional growth based on the subject-scientific approach. We reject a limited understanding of professional growth that equates being professional with being skilful in fulfilling an occupation. For us, the concept of professional growth must necessarily reflect socio-political conditions, which also includes mathematics and mathematics education as academic disciplines. Our reflections have led us to question the relationship between professional practice and research in the process of professional growth.

Introduction: Critical considerations on professional growth

The following reflections are formulated from a specific vantage point: We are at the same time in the position of being researchers and university teachers in the field of mathematics education at a German university. This is a coupling of professional responsibilities, that may be regarded as typical for teacher educators (see, e.g., Adler et al., 2005). Our research focuses on mathematics education at university, which may be considered as atypical in our context. Also, our biographies can be related to the German mathematics education community in terms of typical and atypical aspects: Our employment condition is quite typical, we both have fixed-term contracts. To maintain our 'employability', we need to show our development in both research and university teaching according to the norms prevalent in these two professional fields. We both have quite different educational biographies¹, neither of which is typical within the community. It is inconclusive whether this puts us in a more privileged position.

The starting point for our considerations in this contribution is a critical reflection on our participation in a teaching development project that aimed at strengthen inquiry-based

¹ One of us has a diploma in psychology and a straightforward educational biography. The other one has a working-class background, and not straightforward educational biography with a diploma in mathematics and a master's degree in mathematics education.

mathematics education in higher education². We see this development project as an effort to build up a form of professional development as a shared endeavour. In doing so, professional development should go beyond framing university teachers as in need of being developed by researchers. As a framework, this project works with an adapted form of the Community of Practice approach (Lave & Wenger, 1991). The Community of Practice approach serves as a reference for quite a number of endeavours in the field of the professional development of (university) teachers – that, quite often, intend to fabricate ‘better’ teaching practices. Within this logic, teachers serve as a tool for the provision of (ever changing) ideas of ‘quality’ education. In the following, we do not understand theories on teaching and learning mathematics nor theories on professional growth in terms of a fabrication logic³, but rather as theories that enable us to reflect. To us, reflection goes beyond being a tool for just generating ‘better’ practice, but considers the societal and political constitution of the respective concerns. The project we were involved in emphasised the relationship between professional development of university teachers and inquiry into the field of mathematics education. This focus encouraged us to reflect on the relationship between teaching and research. In our context, the leitmotifs of *education through research* [Bildung durch Wissenschaft] and *unity of teaching and research* [Einheit von Forschung und Lehre] are often referred to (for a critical review see Ricken, 2007). Certainly, these refer to an ideal image of university education and research, which as such is not or has never been fully realised, and it is doubtful to what extent these statements are only (still) used as empty phrases. But then again, these leitmotifs offer us a legitimation to deliberately explore the relationship between research and teaching and its influence on our professional practice as researchers and university teachers in the field of mathematics in higher education. Furthermore, we see a potential for mathematics education at university (both in research and in the further development of the teaching of this field) in reclaiming and interpreting these leitmotifs in relation to our professional interests.

The relationship between research and teaching is negotiated in international discourse under the heading of teaching-research nexus⁴ (Simons & Elen, 2007). There is a wide variety of ways to interpret this nexus. In the following, we do not argue per se for adopting our specific cultural interpretation, such as the leitmotifs *education through research* and *unity of teaching and research*. Rather, we argue for considering this nexus (in its respective culture-

² Partnership for Learning and Teaching in University Mathematics (PLATINUM): <https://platinum.uia.no/>

³ We use ‘fabrication logic’ as a metaphor for summarising homologies in the structures of diverse requirements and rationales (in dealing with those requirements) that we encounter in our context - which often hastily smooth out contradictions and try to resolve them unilaterally with respect to what is possible within the given. This metaphor helps us to question our own thinking with regard to the extent to which we are compliant with such rationales. It offers the possibility of deliberately relate to such rationale.

⁴ It is often understood in a very one-sided way, as good research leads to good teaching. We argue for also considering the other direction.

specific connotations) and possibilities of interpretation when it comes to reflect its potentials in relation to professional interests. We have formulated questions in the discussion section that could aid the reflection and interpretation of this nexus also in other local contexts and positions.

To us, the term professional⁵ goes beyond being skilful in fulfilling an occupation, it always entails a responsibility for a human society (Combe & Helsper, 1996) even though this argument is lost in current discourses about the role of university education (Banscherus, 2015). To act in a professional manner and professional knowledge thus go beyond their reference to an academic discipline. Being professional is more than just expertise, it always also contains the political. It requires a political commitment to the concerns of the respective profession. For us, these are the concerns of education and research, in general, and in the field of mathematics education, in particular.

In our daily experience, efforts in the further development of the teaching profession often follow a hegemonic thinking in the structural organisation of the development process that are based on a hierarchy between experts from an academic field and university teachers thought of as laypersons that are supposedly in need of being developed (Dreier, 2006 on resemblances of schooling, as an institutionalised developmental process, and therapeutic setting and the role of knowledge). Contrary to the trend of decoupling educational and research responsibilities, for example, in a separation of professional development efforts of these two areas, we argue that there is a potential for the further development of research and teaching in its double self-referentiality (*doppelte Selbstbezogenheit*; Reinmann, 2019). The object of research and our position each have a self-referentiality:

The object of our research and of the inquiry in the professional development we participate in is a mathematics education course at university for future teachers. The course presents mathematics education as an academic discipline rather than teaching a mere methods course. Under the header of the leitmotif *education through research*, the course shall introduce the academic discipline of mathematics education, prepare the students for their future profession and contribute to their personal development. The leitmotif *education through research* obliges higher education institutions to establish a link between research and teaching: Teaching shall be conducted in a research-oriented way⁶ (Reinmann, 2019).

⁵ The conception of 'professional' always relates to the actual local formation of the historical bloc. The traditional conception of 'being professional' in our context refers to a model of comparably strong responsibilities of the state for the social sphere compared to the currently, within neoliberalism rising, market-based regulation. Within the traditional idea, 'professions' are independent institutions that are concerned with questions related to the social. The emphasis on the social responsibility is still in use (even though it is also in our context contested) to justify financing and accountability models other than the market-based ones. To us, reclaiming such an idea of 'professionalism' in our context holds the potential to present affiliable arguments that are counter to an individualising, abridged, neoliberal notion of professionalism.

⁶ Both leitmotifs, *education through research* and *unity of research and teaching* are connected. Actually, research should also benefit from teaching. However, this aspect of the *unity of research and teaching* is often lost.

Our inquiry object thus has a specific form of education as its object, which in turn has to do with research in the academic discipline mathematics education. The first self-reference refers to the implicit object of the inquiry: Not only teaching and learning, but also research itself belongs to the inquiry object.

The persons involved in research and that are part of the field that is the object of the research endeavour, are the same in our context, e.g., as researchers in the field of mathematics education and as university teachers to be researched concerning their interaction with students. These roles are not clearly separated (thus always have a share in the educational practice to be researched): Those, in turn, who initially belong to the research object as university teachers, are themselves active in research at the same time. A separation between research and practice, as well as experts and laypersons to be developed, is misleading within the second self-referentiality: a personal involvement in the field of being inquired into, and thus being placed in a position of being the one, who is inquiring, and being part of the research object at the same time.

If we acknowledge the double self-referentiality as being constitutive for the context in which we operate, it does not allow for a supposedly external and neutral standpoint towards the research object. But, often only taking up a neutral stance towards the inquiry object is taken to be appropriate for a research endeavour into one's own teaching and learning. At best, an external shall judge one's development, or the progress displayed in the teaching arrangement. At least, a researcher shall distance her-/himself from one's own personal involvement e.g., through applying supposedly objective measures to evaluate a supposed development, either referring to an enhancement of teaching quality or regarding one's own professional development. In short: One's own involvement is conceived as a confounding variable and potentials within the double self-referentiality are denied.

However, we see our involvement and being affected as an opportunity for broadening our personal and the general professional knowledge base on teaching and learning in tertiary mathematics education. This led us to the question: How can we understand professional growth without relying on a supposedly external and/or neutral point of view as a benchmark and with considering the societal and political constitution of our professional concerns?

Our understanding of professional growth

We conceive professional growth as extending one's own space of action possibilities⁷ (described below) in teaching-learning relations with/in a community of practice. This conceptualisation is inspired by the subject-scientific approach (Holzkamp, 1995, 2013; Dreier, 1999; Ludwig, 2003) and integrates the idea of a situated development within a community of practice (Jaworski, 2004; Lave & Wenger, 1991).

⁷ Action possibility is an analytical category. The analytical categories offered by the subject-scientific approach "conceptualise the mediation between the vital necessities of sustaining the societal system as a whole and these necessities on the subjective level of the discrete individuals" (Holzkamp, 2013, p. 20).

Within the subject-scientific approach, human beings – and therefore learners, teachers and researchers - are perceived as “producers of the life conditions to which they are simultaneously subject” (Holzkamp, 2013, p. 20). It points to consider the conditions, which in our context are specific learning-teaching conditions as well as the conditions of doing research in mathematics education, and it underlines the possibilities of the subject - learners, teachers and researchers - to influence these conditions. The analytical category action possibilities (*Handlungsmöglichkeiten*) grasps possibilities and hindrances to act in and on specific conditions from the standpoint of the subject. Central of thinking in terms of action possibilities is the twofold possibility (*doppelte Möglichkeit*): To either reproduce restrictive conditions or the (however small⁸) possibility to extend established practices and alter socio political conditions. Conditions do not fixate nor determine reasoning, rather conditions are integrated into subjective reasoning with the form of societal-mediated meanings that constitute a space of action possibilities. The subjective-available space of action possibilities is not fixed, but can be extended through conscious engagement. In consequence, we conceptualise professional growth as an extension of the subjective-available space of action possibilities and emphasise the social dimension of this extension process. In alliance with others, it is possible to seize more opportunities for actions and participate in changing conditions that are constraining one’s envisioned practices. Dreier (1999) relates this to community processes:

The fundamental human duality between acting within the existing limits of social practice and extending its scope of possibilities is grounded in a similar duality of modes of participation [in a community], i.e. of participation in the reproduction of the current state of affairs or of contributing to change it so that participants may extend their degree of disposal over the social practice. (p. 6)

Two aspects are important in the formulation “in alliance with others”: Firstly, that one can question one’s own ways of thinking and involvement together with others. And secondly, that one can act together to change things. However, this concern can also be torpedoed by constantly propagating pragmatic solutions and thus creating the impression that there is no need to alter conditions.

To us, an inquiry stance towards teaching and learning means to think in alternatives. In consequence, we do not take current conditions, approaches and theories to teaching-learning mathematics (education) for granted, but question these for its obstructive components and our possibilities to think beyond the narrow horizon of current practices. This objective can be related to an emancipatory objective of academic work that is also of key importance for building up a professional knowledge base (Langemeyer, 2020). Within teaching-learning relations, as well as expert-layperson relations, we often act in a restricted

⁸ This follows the basic assumption that in antagonistic class conditions, the attempt to gain more control over conditions is always accompanied by the risk of getting in conflict with the agents of power and provoking restrictions.

manner, in a modality of alignment with or subjection to given obstructive structures and its logics⁹ – e.g., following a logic that places the teacher in a position of being responsible to fabricate learning and the learners in a position of being in need of further development. But education and professional growth can also be thought of as cooperative activity of being directed towards extending one’s own space of action possibilities, which also includes extending one’s own control over restrictive professional conditions, e.g., in our context teaching-learning relations and research conditions. In alliance with others, it entails the possibility of overcoming obstructions. Research could provide terms for reflecting¹⁰, terms that foster the process of seeking self-understanding for the professional task of teaching. To serve as a reference within the professional knowledge base, we share the conviction, that research in mathematics education needs to integrate social theory and cannot disregard broader societal conditions in the interpretation of phenomena that can be found in teaching-learning. For example, in speaking about our professional growth, we cannot disregard the prevalent norms and interpretations of the research-teaching-nexus. To disregard broader societal conditions would conceal the Political by reducing mathematics education to the development and implementation of teaching tools and strategies and thus constrict mathematics education research.

To interconnect research activity in mathematics education and the teaching and learning of mathematics (education) with each other within a community of practice entails the potential of developing and building on theory that integrates several standpoints of the teaching-learning relations. These standpoints hold the anchor points for the reflective task of decentering from one’s own viewpoint and together, in alliance with others, develop a meta-standpoint.

The collective practice can be understood as supporting an ongoing (self-)understanding process that takes place between the community members and the socio-political conditions in which the professional work is situated. This includes the “reflection of social requirements and conditions in an attempt to (re-)establish self-understanding in individual situations of action and to be able to act in a competent [/professional] manner” (Ludwig, 2003, p. 1, translation by author). The basis for a collegial self-understanding process is the shared socio-political conditions. But how these are perceived and what priorities are assigned by the community members varies. For development with/in a community, it is necessary to understand and penetrate these available perspectives. “Seeking (self-)understanding” refers to the attempt to gain knowledge about and trace one’s own personal and structural entanglement in contradictory situations. In such situations people participate in practices which run counter to their desired practices. By striving for (self-)understanding, we attempt to gain more disposal over our research and teaching practices. Rihm (2006) points out that in our routinised daily work, we often just interpret situations within the

⁹ Safekeeping at the cost of the (re-)production of restrictive conditions.

¹⁰ This requires not just any theory, but necessarily requires theory that doesn’t back or conceal the restrictive structures within the professional knowledge base.

horizon of the typical space of action possibilities of our daily practices – in accordance with professional knowledge base. This means we unquestioningly accept quite a number of aspects of typical ways of working in our professional community. An illustrative example for acting against one's own intentions is detailed in the story of Mrs. Smith that can be found in Cabral & Baldino (2019a). Furthermore, Cabral & Baldino (2019b) reveal that it is compliant in the (re-)production of undesired practices to integrate restrictive conditions in the professional knowledge base by interpreting restrictive conditions as being necessary for the learning process. But "to understand"¹¹ means to gain knowledge about and trace one's own and structural entanglements in contradictory situations, in which we participate in practices counter to our desired practices. Seeking understanding, therefore, means to widen one's own view going beyond the horizon of our everyday entanglement.

This kind of (self-)understanding goes beyond a merely introspective and individual way of progressing (Rhim, 2006): A cooperative de-centering from a personal viewpoint allows to take a meta-standpoint that makes it possible to recognise the interrelation of different research, teaching and learning practices prevalent in society and the collegial group. Reinmann (2019) points out that due to the double self-referentiality, a de-centred reflexivity is necessary in order to adequately address the object of research in higher education teaching and learning. This stands in contrast to other forms of reflection that are intended to ensure an evaluation of one's own performance aimed at an increase in teaching quality. This reflexive distance not only allows to identify supporting and obstructive conditions, but also to recognise potentials of altering conditions.

These potentials can relate to mathematics education research and teaching. As described above, in our context it is not possible to make a precise distinction between research and teaching. In addition, we see a potential for professional growth in the double self-referentiality. We would claim that a professional growth process, conceptualised such as we have described above, is able to contribute to an expansion of the general professional knowledge base. Deliberately, we do not want to outline this possibility in this contribution on the basis of describing any improvements in teaching practices, 'proving' how helpful our reflection has been for the betterment of actual teaching practices. To us, it is impossible to write an "Hollywood-style happy end" (Cabral & Baldino, 2019a, p. 33) without talking down the political and dilute our professional interests.

Discussion: Mathematics education as professional field

We conceptualised professional growth as an extension of the subjective-available space of action possibilities that is constituted by societal-mediated meanings which in turn reflect social conditions. To act professionally means to take responsibility to society into account and goes beyond a mere reference to the academic discipline as a resource for knowledge

¹¹ "Interpreting" is then not opposed to "understanding"; rather, "understanding" simultaneously suspends "interpreting" in itself and transcends it (Holzkamp, 1985, p. 395).

and skills and as an occupational field. To us, the academic discipline, which is the object of professional action, is part of our social conditions.

Expanding and actively shaping our space of action possibilities thus also means the possibility of altering and reshaping conditions. We agree that also the content is political (Gutiérrez, 2013, pp. 9–11). In relation to our academic field, mathematics education, this also means demanding a “say” on questions such as “What is mathematics about?” or “How is the social relevance of mathematics, or a specific mathematics object, to be valued?”. In our understanding, professional responsibility and taking a stance for professional interests requires what Gutiérrez (2013) terms “political *conocimiento*”¹².

In our experience, mathematics and research on the education of mathematics are often taken for granted as exclusively external conditions of professional action. In our context, it is particularly striking that such an assumption does not hold. We argued that considering the double self-referentiality is crucial with respect to our position. In addition, we would question such an externalising construction of relating academic disciplines and professional practices to each other. The academic disciplines of mathematics and education shape the teaching of mathematics (education), but the relation is often interpreted in a one-sided manner: Being skilful in teaching mathematics is equated to fabricating learning environments that transmit and (re-)produce a specific understanding of mathematics. Teaching mathematics (education) certainly is always fabricating an understanding about mathematics and theories on learning. Fabrication logic cannot be ignored or rejected. But it is necessary to think about and go beyond this fabrication process. So, any conception of being professional needs to integrate these aspects. But, a one-sided interpretation of the relation between the academic disciplines and the professional task of education leads to a skewness that restrict the possibilities of its further development.

Looking at the relationship of academic disciplines and professional practices from both sides: First, coming from the perspective of academic disciplines, Schraube and Marvakis (2016, 2019), Holzkamp (2004) and Biesta (2015), besides others, argue against a diminution of teaching-learning theories. In principle, theories can help in a process of reflection that looks beyond what is already possible. However, it is problematic when teaching-learning theories only consider and remain within the boundaries of the currently given, e.g., by integrating restrictive conditions as being quasi-natural conditions for teaching and learning, or conceptualising learning as a process that is only able of reproduction. First, it restricts one’s own thinking about alternatives. Second, theory is a professional basis for legitimating practices. Therefore, practices that potentially look beyond the currently given can be dismissed as illegitimate with reference to narrowed theories. This implies a responsibility for the academic discipline of mathematics education: Providing knowledge for university teachers, regardless of whether they are also active in research in this discipline or not,

¹² Her concept is anchored in a different context and theoretical traditions based thereon. Despite all overlaps in content, we have therefore decided to anchor our argumentation in concepts and theories that are familiar to our context.

means not only providing pragmatic knowledge. It also means providing theories that allow for further development (going beyond what is currently given) and make this visible. Second, coming from the perspective of professional practice, we can note, that the right and opportunity to have a say also depend on the status and understanding of the discipline: If mathematics education is only understood as and presents itself as a promoter for mathematics and service provider for educational policy, then its professional responsibility of furthering mathematical practices for a human society is pushed aside and perishes.

Finally, we would like to emphasise that our reflections have emerged from our context. We have interpreted the teaching-research nexus from our German perspective. In doing so, we are of course not free of the logics prevalent within our field of study. With these reflections on professional growth we wanted to demonstrate a form of thinking in alternatives that, in our context, seems to be suitable to challenge an understanding of professional growth that externalises benchmark criteria.

In our opinion, our understanding of professional growth holds the potential to be generalised, even though it is not directly transferable. So, we would like to conclude our reflections with thinking about implications also for mathematics educators who are working in other contexts and positions. We summarised them in the following questions:

- How can the relationship between research and teaching within the field of mathematics education be thought of in other local contexts?
- What specific leitmotifs and referentialities are relevant for the context and how do these constitute research and teaching in relation to each other?
- Which interpretations of leitmotifs and what referentialities are acknowledged, hold legitimacy, or are ignored? What do they offer for professional growth within the field of mathematics education?

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